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EMERGING TECHNOLOGIES IN THE 21ST CENTURY PEDAGOGY

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Considering the pace at which emerging technologies are evolving, it is crucial that students start to build practical and necessary skills by utilizing adequate tools and resources. Personalized teaching and learning approaches for knowledge acquisition and self-directed learning are facilitated by new pedagogies in which technological advancements are involved. In various educational institutions, the transition from conventional to contemporary methodologies has been able to change their policies, structures, and educational philosophies. The pedagogical experiences of educators and students can be revolutionized through the effective harnessing of emerging technologies. Principles and various teaching methodologies, effective classroom participation and collaboration, deep lesson comprehension, and significant knowledge acquisition can be achieved by integrating and embracing the emerging technologies of this modern era.

This article focuses on the significance and vital roles of various emerging technologies in education. First, Augmented Reality and Virtual Reality foster deep interaction and immersion of learning experiences. Another technology that accommodates educators in providing personalized learning experiences to their learners in order to gain meaningful learning experiences is artificial intelligence. This powerful tool offers data-driven instructional improvement for teachers by automating administrative tasks and giving real-time insights into students' progress. Also, gamification techniques and game-based learning make education more engaging and motivating. Skills such as critical thinking, collaboration, creativity, and problem solving are offered by these kinds of techniques. Blended learning was also introduced, especially when the health crisis started. The benefits of face-to-face instruction and technology-driven tools were optimized by blended learning, which also led to a holistic approach to education. Reshaping the landscape in education is significantly facilitated by blockchain technology.

Additionally, the Internet of Things (IoT) enables institutions to create inclusive, secure, and interactive learning environments, which allows them to prepare for success in this digital age. Robotics and automation in educational institutions cultivate the creativity, problem-solving, and computational skills of learners. These skills equip learners to become more successful in the advancement of this technology-driven world. The significant impact of the Bring Your Own Device approach allows learners to engage themselves with pedagogical contents and collaborate on various activities anytime and anywhere. Through this integration, learners will have continuous, meaningful learnings. More so, Educational Technology, data analytics, and assistive technologies create powerful impacts in the pedagogical process, facilitate personalized learning effectively, provide diverse and equal

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opportunities, address and hurdle barriers among learners, and equip learners to gain the necessary skills and knowledge while ensuring the curriculum is effective and relevant.

In conclusion, the various emerging technologies have valuable roles for making teaching and learning experiences more meaningful. The students can provide relevant insights and deeper understanding about the lessons. Harnessing and integrating these technologies in education, we are able to create well-crafted, inclusive, personalized, and learner-centered teaching and learning experiences. Adapting and embracing all the provided digital-based tools and resources will make the educational system more powerful, and learners will be able to succeed in their future endeavors in this digital world.

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